

Constitutional Travesty in NE State of Manipur

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Abstract

The Constitution *per se* is a unique rule book of India which postulates the mandates of constitutional government to take adequate measures for making an orderly society based on social, economic and political justice. It keeps the government within the legal limits and also reposes people faith on constitutional governance with the sole aim to make free and vibrant society. The universally accepted global norms coupled with the principle of rule of law and constitutionalism remain the only antithesis for arbitrary and capricious powers exercised by the government even during the abnormal situation. The article focuses on implications of preventive detention laws *vis a vis* invocation of the Armed Forces (Special) Powers Act, 1958 and their relative impact in the NE state of Manipur. It also analyses the pro-active judicial responses *inter alia* the sacrosanct concept of inalienable fundamental rights of individuals. Invocation of repressive laws and policies by the responsible government without following the culture of justification has invariably created an adverse impact on citizens and society. Though the constitutional democracy presupposes the majoritarian rule, the principles of consensual rule of both the majority and minority remain to be an inevitable feature in India.

Key words

Colonial legacy, harsh legislation, subjective satisfaction, loyumba silyen, constitutionalism, indigenous people, martial law, black letter law tradition, judicial scrutiny

Introduction

It is the prerogative of legislatures to make and unmake laws, and they do have the opportunity to serve the nation as well as the citizens. Law, as an instrument of change in the society, primarily occupies a significant position in harmonizing the relation

between the ruler and its subjects. Eventually, deep rooted colonial culture of invoking undemocratic repressive measures merely in the name of national unity, security, integrity, law and order has become the general rule rather than an exception. Such inherited colonial legacy has, virtually misled the mindset of people, and in a way, a perpetual manner of incursion on the affairs of inalienable fundamental rights and liberties of individuals has also postulated a serious concern for the legitimate government as well as the general public. A case in point is the enactment and invocation of the Armed Forces (Special) Powers Act, 1958 (AFSPA) in the NE state of Manipur which has, undoubtedly revealed the realities of prolonged issue of human rights violations coupled with a perennial armed conflict in the region. Unwarranted invasion over the citizens' fundamental rights and freedoms has procured a chain of negative reaction from the citizens of the state. Despite the continuous efforts of proactive government initiatives and the constant judicial intervention for mitigating the human sufferings caused by the very invocation of the 1958 Act, the same Act is, unfortunately still remained in the statute book of India and as a result, the perennial issue of conflict has also been lingering ever since in the region without any durable solution.

Constitutional mandate

Legislative measure occupies a significant status and position in a democratic state like India as far as the constitutional scheme is concerned. One of the core objectives for enactment of laws is to protect life and properties of citizens irrespective of all the differences among them. Primarily, law ought to be the expression of the will of general public. That is why an ideal welfare state requires just, fair and reasonable laws that could meaningfully promote and protect the rights and freedoms of citizens of this country. Since the ultimate end of the law is to render justice to all the people without discrimination, law shall not be unjust and it shall not be enforced beyond the prescribed limits as well. It is universally accepted that law is an instrument of social change in a given society and it occupies a significant position in all respects. It always aims to harmonize the relation between the rulers and their subjects, as it is the only connecting link between the two entities. As a matter of fact, it is also inevitable for the responsible constitutional government to construe a good and open governance *inter alia* a healthy

relation between the democratic state and its citizens for which every stockholder shall be mandated to give due respect to the principles of rule of law and constitutionalism so as to bring peace and harmony in the society.

Law makers do have the constitutional prerogative to make and unmake laws for the people and nation. Interestingly, there is a huge space for them to serve the nation and also to protect the citizens through their law-making process. It is also a fact that they do commit trespass over the inalienable rights and freedoms of citizens by enacting and invoking undemocratic laws. In this regard, one may also take into account certain situations where of the legislatures are often circumscribed by the factors of political considerations and other influencing issues, especially while discharging their constitutional obligations. On other hand, the actual practice of law-making process, applied and adopted in India, shows that non-compliance of democratic norms of law-making process, such as, the mandatory rule of consultation with the people, who are likely to be affected by the enactment, is still largely found to be missing. Such kind of aberrations may be analysed by referring to some of the legislative enactments which have been put in place in the NE state of Manipur.

People of India rejected the British rule a long back; however, it seems that majority of them have not yet rejected the past colonial institution as well as its system of governance even after seventy-eight years of its independence. In a way, it may not be so easy to erase such a deep-rooted colonial mindset and their practices within a short period of time; however, the law makers can transform the situation by manifesting new social, political, economic and cultural orders through their constitutional obligation. India adopts and follows written laws in which the constitutional norms coupled with statutory and decisional laws are the only imperative sources and basis in transforming the mindset of people and governance. Mere enactment of harsh legislations for the sake of governing the governance without complying with the universally accepted norms and principles of constitutional democracy, it will not sustain and realize the expected social, economic and political values embedded in the Constitution, instead, people may lose their respect to the responsible constitutional government, and eventually, it may lead to unwarranted situation where the legitimate government and its

agencies may also be unnecessarily dragged in a miserable situation. If people-oriented laws and policies are meaningfully enacted and framed in accordance with the universally accepted standard norms and principles, the prolonged misunderstanding issue between the responsible government and people of the region could have been at least resolved.

Constitutional governance and preventive detention laws

In the context of the NE state of Manipur, history reveals that a written constitution was enacted and adopted from the early period of eleventh century with the aim to set up a constitutional government by the king Meidingu Loiyumba of Manipur in 1078 A.D, which was called Loyumba Silyen. Such a national legal document also recognised and guaranteed certain fundamental rights and liberty of individuals, and as such, the king was placed under the law as well. Therefore, it seems that the very concept of the rule of law and constitutional governance was put in place in the state of Manipur even during the early period. Thereafter, a constitutional monarchy was also established under the Manipur State Constitution Act, 1947, that had recognized and guaranteed fundamental rights and duties of the citizens, such as, the right to life and liberty, right to equality, right to judicial remedy, right to reside, freedom of expression, freedom of religion and freedom of association, among others. Even after, Manipur became a part of the union of India in 1949, the Constitution of India also reaffirmed and reindorsed the similar protection of citizens' rights and freedoms, as incorporated in the Part III and IV of the Constitution. Surprisingly, the Constitution also contains the enabling provision for the state to enact and invoke preventive detention laws. As such, preventive detention is justified under Article 22 of the Constitution by citing the rationality of maintaining national security, integrity, law and order and among others. The reason being is that the law of the land also authorizes the legitimate responsible government to arrest and detain any person on the very subjective satisfaction of the political executive under the preventive detention laws as an extraordinary power. Whereas in some western countries like in UK and USA, the laws of preventive detention are applicable only during the war like situation but not during the peace time, which shows that preventive detention laws are different from the other general criminal laws in term

of their application, objectives and jurisdictions. It is pertinent that the preventive detention laws are normally enacted and enforced not only for punishing the alleged offenders but also for intercepting and preventing them from committing the crimes.

British India history reveals that the very enactment and invocation of preventive detention laws and other special criminal legislations were considered to be very much instrumental in governing the state. Though such past colonial practice alienates the rights and freedoms of individuals, republic of India has been following the same culture of authority by arresting and detaining its own citizens on mere subjective satisfaction considering it as a well set up general rule rather than an exception. It is worth mentioning that one of the largest constitutional democratic countries like India has been following the same suit as an inherited colonial legacy merely on the ground of maintaining national security, unity, integrity and law and order etc. A case in point is the invocation of law of sedition which was one of the bonds of contentions between the British government and the people of India, more particularly during the pre-independent period. Incorporation of seditious law in the old IPC of 1860 and enactment of the Prevention of Seditious Meetings Act, 1911 by the British parliament with the objectives of preventing the freedom of speech and expression *inter alia* freedom of movement of Indian people against the British government were the clear testimonies of legislative measures adopted by the past colonial regime. Under the 1911 Sedition Act, the district civil authority including the civil police has the power to determine on its own whether a particular meeting is a seditious or not. This particular Act can be imposed in any part or whole of state by a legitimate government. Even today, such colonial nature of statutory Act has neither been repealed nor amended. The concerned legitimate government is empowered to declare certain area as the proclaimed area and also authorized to lift the same according to its subjective satisfaction, as such, government of Manipur has declared under the Prevention of Seditious Meetings Act, 1911, two districts namely, Bishnupur and Thoubal as the proclaimed areas in the state. Similarly, the same proclamation was also extended by the government of Manipur to four districts namely, Churachandpur, Chandel, Ukhrul and Senapati with effect from 5th June, 2000.

In aftermath of Indian independence, the Preventive Detention Act, 1950 was enacted by the parliament of India with objective to prevent any person from acting in a manner prejudicial to the defence of India, the relation of India with foreign powers, the security of India or a state and also for the maintenance of supplies and services of essential commodities to the community; however, the said Act was heavily criticised from different quarters and as such, it was scrapped from the statute book of India. Thereafter, the Maintenance of Internal Security Act (MISA), 1971 was passed by the parliament, which came into force from the 2nd July, 1971. The Act was again amended in July 1975 during the national emergency and the power of judicial scrutiny was also taken away by the said Amendment Act. In addition, the grounds of arrest and detention of individuals under the Act were not to be communicated to the detainees, and as such, the Act could not be challenged in any court of law. Eventually, union of India repealed the MISA in August 1979; however, a similar preventive detention law was again put in place by the government on 22nd September 1980 by promulgating the National Security Ordinance of 1980, later, it was replaced by the National Security Act of 1980 (NSA). The core objective for invoking the NSA in the region was to combat with the emerging situation of insurgency movement, communal disharmony, external activities, internal violence and social unrest, among others.

Invocation of AFSPA, 1958

In every human civilization, repressive measure was the usual practice adopted by the rulers elsewhere in the world with the main objective to subjugate and quell down the people movement against rulers; however, after the end of colonial era, such anti-people measure has no place, especially in the constitutional democracy. The man-made repressive measure, either be legislative, administrative or military, had never succeeded in resolving any kind of politically motivated conflict in the human history. Surprisingly, a new version of such legislative measure like the invocation of AFSPA, 1958, which contains the colonial versions of British India, is *per se* the re-incarnation of the Armed Forces Ordinance of 1942. Enactment and invocation of the AFSPA was basically to quell down the issue uprising in the Naga Hills of North East India, which might, in other word, be assumed for legitimizing the continuation of colonial measures

within the free Indian territory. Mr. G.B. Pant, then the Home Minister of India, while discussing the matter in the parliament, assured that the AFSPA was enacted and invoked purely as a temporary measure. However, there was no much debate on the issue in the parliament except the two MPs from Manipur who had strongly resisted against the passing of such repressive Act.

One of the primary objectives of the 1958 Act was to contain the ethnic uprising issue which took place in a small part of the republic of India. However, during the passage of time, the actual intention for passing the Act seems to be overshadowed, and it is also evident that there has been a nuclear chain of reaction from the people of NE states ever since the Act has been put in place in the region. In a way, it has turned to be a kind of resilience of the past infamous conditional legislation used and followed by the British India. The AFSPA confers unbridled powers on the armed forces personnel with virtual immunity and impunity once the region has been declared as disturbed area under the Act. As matter of fact, the existing criminal laws of India seem to be quite adequate in dealing with the issue of internal violence, national security, peace and integrity in the region even without resorting to such undemocratic legislations like AFSPA of 1958. It may be noted that the mightier the state repression, the wider the discontent and proliferation of politically motivated people movement would, obviously be unfolded in the region.

Relative impact of AFSPA

Eventually, such enactment and invocation of repressive measures in the name of maintenance of social order, counter-insurgency, public safety, national unity and integrity, among others, more particularly in the NE state of Manipur have, perhaps allowed the representative government to inherit the colonial legacy of enjoying unbridled authority of maintaining government secrecy, privileges, impunity and immunity. As a result, it has, eventually been triggering off the situation deeper and deeper in a multiple ways and dimensions rather than mitigating the situation. It is evident that the state of Manipur becomes socially, politically and historically a trouble torn-state in the NE India ever since she has become a part of union of India from 1949. Movement of insurgency, militant, guerrilla, national liberation and separatist have also

grown up leading to a perennial armed conflict situation in the region. The case in point is the perpetual invocation of AFSPA, 1958 and its relative impact of unbridled powers with virtual impunity conferred on armed forces personnel who are deployed for maintenance of public order in the region. Law enforcing agencies of central governments operating under said Act are immune from the legal tangle for their illegal and arbitrary actions against citizens. This piece of legislation has almost overturned the avenues of available remedies for the victims of human of rights violations, and the actual perpetrators of human rights violations have also been allowed to get scot-free without any legal rider.

The infamous judgement held by the apex court of India in NPHMR vs Union of India (1997), despite its Does and Don't guidelines, justified the principles of secrecy, privileges and impunity enjoyed by the armed forces personnel deployed under the 1958 Act, and the same verdict of the Supreme Court unfortunately overlooked the legal implications of international human rights laws and the constitutionalism of India. As such, the Court also did not consider the binding international obligations of India, as set forth in the multilateral international treaties to which she had so far acceded. Whereas the universally accepted principles of rule of law and constitutionalism invariably keep ensuring that every victim of human rights violation can resort to appropriate judicial remedies available under the existing legal system. Invocation of such repressive measure even during the time of public emergency normally poses serious criticism; however, if it is imposed perpetually during the normal peace time that too without making legitimate declaration of public emergency as per the law of the land, it will, obviously be a counter-productive that may ignite the conflict situation in the region. Defying the culture of justification has, eventually resulted an adverse impact on the mindset of people almost in all respects. Instead of resorting to such colonial culture of authority, the responsible government could have applied and adopted the culture of justification in its endeavours. In addition, without using the special legislative measure, the existing general criminal laws and procedures of India may be used and applied for all reasons and purposes like what the responsible government has been doing in the affected areas of Naxalite movement in different parts of India.

In way, invocation of repressive measures by the responsible government may also link with the resultant impact of globalization and urbanization, simply because by endorsing the emerging global trends of international human rights and humanitarian regimes, the development may even facilitate unwarranted fragmentation among the indigenous people, and subsequently, it may also promote the identity clash, communal violence and ethnic clash in which politically motivated brokers shall often get a chance of manufacturing the tension between the conflicting groups for their own political benefits. One of the glaring testimonies was the Meitei and Kuki conflict in the NE region of Manipur that broke out in May 2023. Therefore, the reason for protection of indigenous people identity, culture, language, place, religion etc. in the NE state of Manipur has relatively turned to be one of the complicated issues for the legitimate responsible government as well. It seems that every indigenous community has started asserting its own rights and freedoms based on its land, language, culture and place, among others since their rights are legally accorded by the international human rights laws. The adoption of 1995 UN Declaration of Rights of Indigenous People, the movement of indigenous people in the region has also rapidly grown up its momentum. It is also a fact that during the last two decades, a number of communities based underground outfits have been found increasingly on the rise in the region leading to irreparable segregation among the people within their own home land.

Judicial response

The Constitution of India is, undoubtedly a unique in its nature, scope and contents. The constitutional authorities not only obtain their mandates from the Constitution but they are also obligated to follow and function in accordance with the written and unwritten constitutional laws. Indeed, AFSPA is neither a martial law, preventive detention law nor an emergency legislation as per the constitutional law of India is concerned, but it is certainly a unique special legislation found to be in the statute book of India which nevertheless contravenes the universally accepted doctrine of rule of law and the constitutionalism in one way or other. In this regard, it may also be noted that Article 21 of the Constitution has, virtually become an enabling proviso of the Constitution for the state to enact and invoke laws which can take away one's life and liberty under the

pretext of the term “procedure established by law”. Apparently, it stands to be immaterial for the state to determine whether the AFSPA is a just law or unjust law for the simple reason is that the Act has been enacted in compliance with the doctrine of “procedure established by law” as set forth in the Article 21 of the Constitution. However, the liberal interpretation of Article 21 by the apex court of India in *Maneka Gandhi vs Union of India* (1978) has proved that the “procedure established by law” shall not be unfair, arbitrary or unreasonable, and it shall be just, fair and reasonable; therefore, it clearly indicates that even the legislative action shall not be out of the judicial scrutiny.

The Supreme Court judgement of *NPHMR vs Union of India* (1997) pertaining to the constitutionality of AFSPA, which was delivered after a period of 17 years of its pending in the same court needs to be revisited in the light of various emerging dimensions and dynamics. Deprivation of avenues for the victims of AFSPA seems to be overlooked by the court which can't be accepted by any civilized legal system in the world; besides, the principles of just, fair and reasonable procedure established by law, as laid down in *Maneka's* case in 1978 by the same court, has not been reflected at all in the 1997 judgement. The apex court also sidelined the international obligations of India, as set forth in the international multilateral human rights treaties to which the union of India had acceded. It apparently shows the testimony of applying so called the doctrine of black letter law tradition that was prevailing during the British India period. The apex court did not mention the international obligations of government of India in its deliberation of 1997 judgement, instead, it had confined on the literal interpretation of statutory provisions by following its traditional formalities within the limited legal framework. Surprisingly, the court referred to many provisions of the international human rights laws as well in many of its past verdicts even before 1997.

As a matter of fact, change itself is the life of law, the existing statutory bodies like the NHRC established under the Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993 can also adopt the same suit in facilitating to repeal the AFSPA, like the way what the NHRC had done to the deletion of the TADA,1987. In a way, Indian judicial system allows the aggrieved individuals of the court verdict to file review petition or even curative petition against

such 1997 judgement in a larger constitutional bench of the same court, but it may not be so easy as it is commonly believed to be, simply because the larger constitutional bench may also likely to follow the same as that of the 1997 judgement simply by upholding the importance of national issue rather than by upholding the sacrosanct concept of citizen's life and liberty. Nevertheless, the AFSPA blatantly violates the basic tenets of international human rights documents to which govt. of India has been one of the signatory states. It is also worth mentioning that some of the recommendations submitted by the legitimate authorities, like the Justice Jeevan Reddy Committee, the Administrative Reforms Committee and Santosh Hedge Committee among others have, apparently revealed the need and essentiality of repealing the Act. In a similar manner, the international human rights bodies, such as the UN Human Rights Committee, UN Rapporteurs and Amnesty International among others, have also been repeatedly making such similar observations for repealing the 1958 Act. Despite the strong people resistance movements against such undemocratic repressive law, the AFSPA is still found to be rigorously enforced in the region almost in perpetual manner.

Conclusion

A wide range of legislative as well as administrative measures enforced in the NE state of Manipur needs to be revisited in the light of the emerging global and national standards. Constitutional apparatus can't alone realise the expected goals of a welfare state as set forth in the law of the land. It is equally significance for all functionaries of the state including general public to participate and involve honestly in the process of making a meaningful constitutional government and also in resolving the conflict once for all; the reason being is that people's participation in a constitutional democracy is both the means as well as the ends for a good governance. In a way, those people-oriented welfare measures adopted by the responsible government have also primarily focussed on core objectives to change the condition of citizens' life by reaching, sensitising and moulding the mindset of the general masses; however, such plethora of public oriented endeavours, undertaken by the different agencies of the state, seem to have long overdue in realizing the basic objectives set forth in the Constitution. Any kind of positive reform in a given society either it is a social, political or economic

transformation, the first pre-condition is to change the mindset of the concerned individuals. This is what a welfare state is expected to be, otherwise this would, eventually pose a serious threat to the very concept of constitutional democracy.

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